

Effects of different interaction mechanisms
between hypothetical gravions and matter
on Push Gravity theories

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Push Gravity

This work investigates details of the Push Gravity (PG) theory introduced by Fatio de Duillier in 1690 [Wikipedia contributors (2018a)], documented by Le Sage in 1748 [Wikipedia contributors (2018b)] and elaborated mathematically by Danilatos in 2020 [Danilatos, G. (2020)]. The detailing of the work at hand is with respect to the mechanism of interaction between hypothetical “gravions” (as introduced by Danilatos) and matter.

Danilatos assumes absorption of gravions and re-emission of gravions of a different type in order to overcome the energy problem of push gravity theories. The work at hand discusses alternative interactions, especially isotropic and anisotropic scattering of gravions at matter particles.

Figure 1: Principle idea of Push Gravity: Isotropic repulsive gravion radiation being reduced by the earth beyond the apple, resulting in an effective force pushing the apple towards the earth

The idea of Push Gravity is shown in figure 1. A nearly isotropic and homogeneous radiation of gravions with radiance S_0 is coming from all directions of space, comparable to the cosmic microwave background. Objects reduce the radiation according to a Beer-Lambert damping law to $S(x) = S_0 \cdot e^{-\alpha \cdot x}$, where x is the length the radiation passes through the object, and the damping coefficient $\alpha = \rho \cdot \Lambda$ is proportional to the objects mass density ρ and the yet unknown proportionality factor Λ .

For low damping coefficients the linearization $S(x) \approx S_0 \cdot (1 - \alpha \cdot x)$ of the exponential damping law leads to the known form of Newton’s law of gravitation $F_G = G \cdot \frac{M \cdot m}{r^2}$, resolving Newton’s

gravitational constant G with the parameter Λ , the radiance S_0 , and the speed of light c by the relation $G = \frac{\Lambda^2 \cdot S_0}{c}$. The speed of light is introduced by the assumption that the pressure p of completely absorbed gravion radiation with irradiance E is given in the same way as the pressure by absorbed electromagnetic radiation by the relation $p = \frac{E}{c^2}$.

The work of Danilatos shows a detailed derivation of the above relations and calculates and discusses many aspects where Push Gravity deviates from Newton's theory of gravity, especially for objects with high values of $\alpha \cdot R$, where R is the radius of the object.

Optical analogy simulations

The performed optical simulations make use of the analogy of scattering of light by semitransparent material with scattering of gravions by the mass density of matter. The used simulation software was the optical ray tracing software Ansys Speos in version 2023 R1.

Scattering processes in general may be divided into elastic, inelastic, and completely inelastic processes, depending on the portion of energy that is converted into inner energy of the participating objects. Completely inelastic scattering is related to an absorption process as one participant disappears.

A second differentiation can be made between coherent and incoherent scattering processes.

A third differentiation can be made regarding the ratio of the masses of participating objects. The higher the ratio of masses the smaller is the transferred energy. As the used optical software does not consider any energy transfer, for the numerical investigations in this work an infinite mass ratio is assumed. It is recommended to investigate the influence of a finite mass ratio in future work.

For the investigations in the paper at hand only incoherent elastic scattering and completely inelastic scattering (absorption) was simulated, as they are sufficient to show in which conditions push gravity can create attractive forces.

Figure 2 shows the simulation setup in the optical simulation software Ansys Speos representing two different spherical masses and an evaluation plane between both objects. This setup may be interpreted as a scaled principal model of the earth and the moon.

For astronomical objects like planets and moons it is expected $\alpha \cdot R \ll 1$. Thus, the gravion radiation is expected to be influenced very weakly by those objects, so the major portion of the radiation passes through these objects and only a very small portion of the radiation is absorbed and/or scattered by the objects.

To get numerically stable results in the used optical software, which is designed for typical optical devices with a size of millimeters to meters, the size of earth and moon were scaled by a factor of 10^{-9} .

To reduce computational cost the distance of earth and moon was scaled even more. As the ray tracing software Ansys Speos is stochastically calculating a huge number of rays the effects under investigation would require much more rays to get statistically significant results if the real distance would be considered. But to qualitatively show the principle effects this simplified model is appropriate.

Figure 2: Simulation model setup in Ansys Speos

The probability for scattering of a ray per length of its path is described by a parameter with units of mm^{-1} that is called diffusion coefficient in Ansys Speos. Other sources name it scattering coefficient.

In the scaled model the bigger sphere (earth) has a radius of 6.37mm, the smaller sphere (moon) has a radius of 1.74mm.

In Ansys Speos the anisotropic scattering behavior is described by a table of relative amplitudes depending on the scattering angle. Figure 3 shows an example table for a scattering characteristics with mainly backscattering in 170° - 180° direction.

As a source of light a surrounding uniform ambient light source with a luminance of $1000cd/m^2$ was applied.

Figure 3: Extremely anisotropic backwards scattering

In push gravity theory according to [Danilatos, G. (2020)] the assumed absorption coefficient is not yet known. While several hints on possible ranges are given in [Danilatos, G. (2020)] the values used for simulation here are chosen just in a way to get significant qualitative results with acceptable computational effort.

Configurations

The following configurations were investigated:

1. Absorption without re-emission
2. Absorption with isotropic re-emission of identical gravions
3. Scattering with isotropic scattering characteristics
4. Scattering with anisotropic scattering characteristics
5. Multiple scattering

Configuration 1 was investigated by modelling an absorption coefficient of 0.1 mm^{-1} and no scattering.

Configuration 2 and 3 are the same from momentum transfer point of view, and are investigated by modelling an isotropic scattering coefficient and no absorption.¹

Between configuration 4 and 5 there is a smooth transition depending on the used diffusion coefficient. A low diffusion coefficient results in mainly single scattering processes, while higher

¹ The difference between configuration 2 and 3 would only become relevant if the coherence of the radiation would be included in the investigation. As long as knowledge about the nature of gravions and a potential wavelength of gravion radiation is not available, there is no need to think about coherent scattering.

values of the diffusion coefficient increase the probability of multiple scattering processes for each gravion inside each object. So, to show the principle behavior with low computational cost a reasonable diffusion coefficient of 0.1 mm^{-1} was chosen for configuration 4 and compared to the results of a calculation with diffusion coefficient 0.3 mm^{-1} provoking multiple scattering for configuration 5. The angular dependency shown in figure 3 was used for this purpose.

Results

Configuration 1

Figure 4 shows the drop of irradiance on the evaluation plane between the two massive objects in configuration 1 (absorption without re-emission). The illuminance drops from nearly 3000lx down to nearly 500lx. This, of course, is the expected behavior for absorption without re-emission of the gravions.

Figure 4: irradiance on the evaluation plane between objects in configuration 1

The drop in irradiance between the two spheres means a lower gravion pressure between the spheres than coming from outer space. So, a drop in irradiance means an attractive force for the considered configuration.

Configuration 2 and 3

For configuration 2 and 3 no variation of irradiance is found on the evaluation plane. This is reasonable as the radiation situation of configuration 2 and 3 can be compared to a thermal radiation problem in thermal equilibrium.

Configuration 4

Figure 5 shows the drop of irradiance on the evaluation plane between the two massive objects in configuration 4. The maximum relative drop is about 1%. This is a less significant drop than in configuration 1, but still obvious and statistically significant. This result means that also with the process of anisotropic scattering the pushing gravion radiation between the two objects is weaker than the pushing gravion radiation coming from undisturbed space, and the resulting forces push the two objects towards each other.

Figure 5: Irradiance on the evaluation plane between objects in configuration 4 with a

Configuration 5

In configuration 5 the simulated relative drop is smaller than in configuration 4. This behavior can be explained, as multiple anisotropic scattering statistically reduces the anisotropy of the resulting final scattering angle compared to the original incident angle.

Thus the attractive force is still there as in configuration 4 but is getting smaller instead of higher.

It is expected that there is a range of the anisotropic scattering coefficient starting from 0 where the attractive force increases with the scattering coefficient, reaches a maximum for a certain value of the scattering coefficient, and then decreases with a further increasing scattering coefficient. This hypothesis should be investigated by further simulations.

Summary

The ray tracing simulations for different interaction mechanisms between the radiation of Push Gravity gravions and matter are summarized in table 1. The table lists for which assumptions attractive forces similar to Newton's law of gravitation occur, and for which assumptions no attractive force results.

1. Absorption without re-emission	Attractive force
2. Absorption with isotropic re-emission of identical gravions	No attractive force
3. Scattering with isotropic scattering characteristics	No attractive force
4. Scattering with anisotropic scattering characteristics	Attractive force
5. Multiple scattering (high $\alpha \cdot R$)	Reduced attractive force

Table 1: Summary of simulation results for different absorption and scattering configurations

As the interaction mechanisms with anisotropic scattering help solving the energy problem of Push Gravity theory this result encourages to investigate Push Gravity further as an alternative gravitational theory.

These results were first presented by the author on 22 March 2023 in Dresden, Germany, at the Spring conference 2023 of the section matter and cosmos (SmuK) of the German Physical Society (DPG) in a German talk named »Was, wenn die Grundkraft "Gravitation" grundsätzlich abstoßend wirkt?« (»What if the basic force 'gravity' is basically repulsive?«)

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